

Table 1. Reaction of the Ranchi GM biotype and of 6 established biotypes to 5 differential varieties.

Origin	Reaction ^a				
	Eswarakora group	Siam 29	OB677 derivative	PTB derivative	Leaug 152
China	R	R	R	S	—
Indonesia	S	R	R	S	R
Sri Lanka	S	R	R	R	R
India (Andhra Pradesh)	R	R	R	R	R
India (Orissa)	S	R	R	R	R
Thailand	R	S	S	S	S
India (Ranchi)	R	S	S	MR	S

^aR = resistant, MR = moderately resistant, S = susceptible.

Table 2. Evaluation of rice cultivars for field resistance to GM.

Score ^a	Cultivars
0	RP1579-92-85-203
1	RP2199-3-3-5-1, RP2190-104-64-18-1, RP2434-24-2-2, Phalguna
3	RP2235-163-33-8, RP2235-48-54-6, RP2091-272-34-8, WGL 48684, R270-3188, RP2431-6-62, RP2434-79-2-6
5	Rp1125-606-637-1, W1125-630-667~1, RP1125-638-1-1, RTN81, RP2435-50-1, RP2434-24-1-2, RP2434-22-3-3, RP1579-34-54, RP2235-136-65-10, RP2235-91-15-1, RP1579-43, RP1579-43-48, CR400-16, CR406-16, OR447-3, RP2199-32-30-47-46, RP1607-1629-44-221, RP1606-29-232, RP2431-5-3-4
7	RP1125-604-1-1, RP1125-637-673-1, RP2199-84-2, WGL 44645, RP2432-34-3-1, RP2432-34-3-4, RP2434-22-3-2, RP1579-38-48, RP1579-36-33, RP2235-85-62-8, RP2235-62-33-1, RP2199-34-6-1, CR404-6, CR400-15, CR404-9-1, R278-3528, OR633-7, RP2199-3-3-3-2, RP1528-86-43-220, RP1579-59-227, RP2434-79-2-4, RP2434-22-3-3, Vikas
9	RP2432-34-4-5, RP2432-34-5-4, OR706-4, RP2432-34-3-4, RP2432-34-5-1, Jaya

^aBased on *Standard evaluation system for rice scale*.

were screened against GM. The genotypes were sown in 4.50- × 2.0-m plots at 20- × 15-cm spacing with 2 replications. All recommended agronomic cultural practices were used.

Maximum GM infestation was in the last week of Sep to the first week of Oct. At 50 d after transplanting, 15 randomly selected hills were scored for number of hills having silvershoot and for number of silvershoots/infested hill. Susceptible checks Jaya and Vikas had severe infestation (more than 40%).

No silvershoots were found in RP1579-92-85-203. Resistance levels of cultivars are given in Table 2. Cultivars scoring 0-3 can be used as donor parents in the breeding programs. □

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Resistance of rice varieties to brown planthopper (BPH), whitebacked planthopper (WBPH), and gall midge (GM) in India

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BPH, WBPH, and GM cause substantial yield losses in Chattisgarh region (the rice bowl of Madhya Pradesh State). We screened about 400 accessions using the standard seedbox screening technique at Hyderabad 1983-87. For BPH and WBPH, damage was scored on the *Standard evaluation system for rice scale* 1-9; absence of silvershoots was rated resistant to GM.

Entries with damage scores 5 or lower in replicated tests are presented in the table. Most of these varieties possess resistance to one pest; Bhakwa was resistant to both BPH and GM. □

Test lines with damage scores of 5.0 or lower against BPH, WBPH, and GM at Hyderabad, India.

Accession no.	Cultivar	Damage score
<i>Brown planthopper</i>		
A440	Anjania	4.1
A61 _i	Bainspath	5.0
B2112	Bhakwa	5.0
C62 _{iii}	Chhatri	3.8
---	E.B. 17	4.7
K2351	Kabari	2.0
L289 _{ii}	Lalbasant	4.1
S644	Safedhdhanwar	1.9
<i>Whitebacked planthopper</i>		
	Batri	2.9
D307 _i	Dihula	3.0
DI061	Dihula	2.8
DI064	Dihula	2.7
---	Karanphool	3.0
---	Khalasu	2.0
<i>Gall midge</i>		
B2712	Bhakwa	Resistant
	Dehradodi	Resistant
	Gurmatia	Resistant
	Jhitpiti	Resistant
	Kudunjan	Resistant
	Lalbogri	Resistant
	Tulasimanjari	Resistant
	Viruppu	Resistant

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